

Research Papers

Mapping the flow: Knowledge development and diffusion in the global innovation system of flow battery technology

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ABSTRACT

Redox flow batteries (RFB) are receiving increasing attention as promising stationary energy storage systems. However, while first innovation activities in this technological field date back to the 1950s, the commercialization and diffusion rates of RFB technology have remained limited. Apart from technological challenges, the lack of a functioning innovation system is one of the main barriers to mainstream this technology. Here, we carried out a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of the RFB research field to shed systematic light on a core aspect of innovation systems - the production of knowledge. Based on the analysis of 4,872 papers published in the years 1981–2021, we reveal developments over time, describe the geographical distribution of research activities, and explore collaboration networks as well as emerging lines of research. Overall, our study allows for strengthening the RFB innovation system by providing the foundation for aligning a scattered research field, identifying needs for technology development, and fostering collaboration and synergy creation.

1. Introduction

Together with the ongoing electrification of the global energy economy, global population growth, urbanization, and industrialization processes of developing economies continue to amplify energy demand rates all over the world [1]. Raising the share of renewable energy resources in the world energy split is pivotal for bending the global greenhouse gas emissions curve down and reaching the Paris Agreement (2015) goal of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C compared to preindustrial levels [2]. In its roadmap to a climate-compatible energy system, the International Renewable Energy Agency projected that by the year 2050, 85 % of the globally generated electricity will have to come from renewable sources [3]. While it remains to be seen if this projection will be realized, there is currently a clear upward trend in the diffusion of renewable energy technologies, with the share of renewables in the global electricity mix being expected to increase from 29 % in 2022 to 35 % in 2025 [4].

A higher share of variable renewables in total electric power generation will require more efficient and large-scale stationary energy storage systems (ESS) [5]. Effective energy storage (ES) technology can address power fluctuations caused by the intermittent nature of

renewable energy sources, improve energy efficiency and self-sufficiency of power plants and provide power supply backup solutions in case of emergency [6]. Moreover, it can potentially decrease electricity costs for distributors and consumers with the integration of hourly pricing policies by electric companies [7].

According to the Global Energy Storage Database, almost 98 % of currently installed energy storage is attributed to pumped storage hydropower (PSH) (169,557 MW) followed by Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries (1629 MW), which constitutes almost half of the installed capacities, when excluding the dominating PSH technology [8]. Both PSH and Li-ion technologies have important disadvantages. Although PSH plants are considered to be highly efficient, they are suitable only for high-power long-time services due to the inability to satisfy fast power demand [9,10]. Furthermore, the construction of PSH plants is highly dependent on local topography, associated with environmental impacts, and has a low acceptance rate among the population [11,12]. Li-ion batteries, in turn, are only suited for storage duration periods of several hours, but not of several days – a prerequisite for the future energy system with a high share of intermittent renewables [6,13]. In addition, Li-ion batteries are associated with scarcity of resources and safety risks [12,14].

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Against this background, there is a search for alternative ESS systems. A technology that receives increasing attention in this context is a redox flow battery (RFB). Although the installed capacity of RFB systems accounts for <2 % of all globally deployed energy storage systems [8], they are regarded as a promising stationary energy solution [12,14,15]. The main advantages of RFBs include flexible and virtually unlimited scalability of capacity, as well as independent sizing of power output and energy storage attributed to the specific design of the battery. Particularly vanadium-based RFBs have shown high round-trip efficiency, high depth of discharge, long durability of >20 years, fast response rate, reduced environmental impact, and high operational safety [7,12,13,16–19]. Flow batteries also proved to be suitable for energy management, integration with renewable energy sources for back-up, emergency back-up power, ramping and load following, black-start, voltage regulation and control and grid/network fluctuation suppression [20].

Despite many advantages of RFBs, the upscaling of this technology remains challenging [12,21] and the number of publications describing deployment of kW scale RFBs is limited, with a few actors and companies capable of installing large systems [21–26]. Although the development of the RFB technology dates back to 1954 [27], the lack of 'first markets' and production experience contributes to the perception of an RFB as a riskier option compared to Li-ion batteries [15,28]. Furthermore, the most mature RFB systems are based on vanadium, which is a (toxic) metal and thus associated with supply and sustainability issues [29,30]. Finally, the high proliferation of cheaper Li-ion batteries, whose costs have been constantly dropping because of innovation and economies of scale, makes the competition for RFBs with higher installation costs more challenging [31,32]. However, in terms of the levelized costs of storage (LCOS), RFB batteries already compete with Li-ion batteries in certain scenarios [76]. The LCOS considers all costs related to the installation (capital costs), operation, maintenance and end-of-life costs. These costs are divided by the power (€/kW) and the storage capacity (€/kWh) the battery can achieve during its lifetime. Both, achievable power and storage capacity depend on the charge/discharge profile, the number of cycles which the energy storage system can be used for, as well as other operation conditions. The capital costs are typically the largest contribution in the LCOS and current efforts aim to reduce these by a variety of strategies, including cost reduction by change of redox chemistry but also by extending the electrochemical window of water in certain setups [33]. This would increase design flexibility for redox cells, as it would also allow for using more expensive chemistries in an economic manner due to an increase in efficiency [34]. This is a strategic advantage over Li-ion battery technology as it represents a flexible strategy to improve performance.

Despite good prospects for increasing competitiveness, currently even the most commercialized RFB variants are not fully optimized and can be still considered a niche technology. As such, more efforts are needed to reach a widespread adoption of the technology. According to the technological innovation system (TIS) literature [35,36], this also includes the broadening and deepening of the existing knowledge base. The TIS approach emphasizes that the development, diffusion and utilization of novel technologies is embedded in a wider 'innovation system' of actor networks and institutional structures [37]. While the existence of a strong knowledge base is seen as a prerequisite for the functioning of such innovation systems [38,39], little is known about the development and diffusion of knowledge and the associated directions of search in the field of RFB research. In this paper, we thus provide a comprehensive overview of the RFB research field by carrying out a bibliometric analysis. Specifically, we analyze publication trends, describe the geographical distribution of research efforts, and reveal collaboration networks as well as emerging lines of research within the field. With the rising demand for energy storage solutions, many bibliometric studies on energy storage systems were published recently, including studies in the fields of thermal energy storage (e.g., [40–44]), hydrogen energy storage systems [45–47], compressed air energy

storage [48,49] or Li-ion batteries [50,51]. However, a comprehensive bibliometric study on the RFB research field is currently missing.

2. Bibliometrics

The research methodology flow is presented in Fig. 1. The sample of publications was obtained in May 2022 using the search string TITLE-ABS-KEY({redox flow battery} OR {redox-flow battery} OR {redox flow batteries} OR {redox-flow batteries} OR {flow battery} OR {flow batteries}). The following way of formulating a search string was based on pre-screening of common keywords in the RFB literature and allowed excluding papers not directly related to the RFB research field. The Scopus database was used as a source of data as it had more records compared to the Web of Science. The search was limited to articles, reviews, and conference papers written in English and published before and including 2021. Publications after 2021 were excluded, as records were not yet complete at the time of the data sampling. The first paper in the dataset was published in 1981. After removing duplicates and additional manual filtering based on the language parameter, 4,872 records were subjected to the analysis. Overall, there were 3907 articles (80 %), 656 conference papers (14 %), and 309 reviews (6 %) in the analyzed corpus.

Prior to the analysis, the necessary data for the study was cleaned and refined, using a web-based software OpenRefine, manually in Excel or in R. Authors' names were harmonized with an additional review of the top 30 most publishing authors and the top 30 authors with the highest h- and m- indexes to ensure that each author's short name represents a single author. The authors' affiliations and addresses were harmonized. The citation style of 70 most cited and most recent publications within the database were harmonized; this was deemed sufficient for the analysis as further refinement did not bring significant changes into the results of the local citation analysis.

It was decided to use the authors' keywords for the keyword-based analysis as many thematic inconsistencies were observed in the indexed keywords. However, the authors' keywords also required considerable cleaning: Synonyms such as 'flow battery' and 'redox flow battery' were merged, spelling errors were corrected and words not related to the research goal, such as 'Germany' or 'review', were deleted. To allow a deeper understanding of emerging and dominating topics in the research field, refined authors' keywords were thematically clustered (Appendix A). Additionally, too general keywords such as 'energy storage' or 'chemistry' were attributed to a "No cluster" group.

The refined dataset ($N = 4,872$) was analyzed and visualized using the R-based bibliometric tool 'Biblioshiny' [52] (Figs. 5, 8 and 10), or manually in Microsoft Excel. For the author impact analysis, research output (i.e., absolute number of publications in the dataset) was chosen as a defining parameter. That allowed to produce the results consistent with other analyses performed in Biblioshiny (i.e., authors' research output over time and collaboration network), which are also based on this metric. In terms of the total global citations (i.e., the number of times the author was cited for their publications from the database within and beyond the RFB research field), it is important to note that the data on the global citations as presented here was extracted in May 2022. Total local citations refer to the number of times the authors were cited for their publications within the dataset. The proportion of the number of publications in the database in relation to the global number of publications was calculated from the year when a researcher entered the RFB field (i.e., their first publication in the database) until June 2023 (the month when the information was retrieved from the researchers' profiles on Scopus).

For the affiliation and country analyses, it is important to differentiate between 'research output' (i.e., absolute number of publications by an affiliation or country in the dataset) and 'scientific productivity' (i.e., number of times an affiliation or country was mentioned in the authors' addresses column for corresponding publication), as the latter allows for counting of a single publication for the same affiliation or country more

Fig. 1. Research methodology flow.

than once. Whereas only scientific productivity was used for affiliation impact analysis (performed in Biblioshiny), both parameters were included in the analysis of scientific activity of countries (performed manually). The research output of countries was further used for the calculation of scientific impact (average citations per paper: total global citations divided by research output), as total global citations were counted for a single country only once, regardless of how many different affiliations from this specific country contributed to the publication. Research output was also used in the analysis of countries' activity in the field over time and in the analysis of spatial distribution of research on alternative materials.

Another parameter used in the assessment of countries' activity in the research field is a share of multiple country publications (performed in Biblioshiny); only papers with the address(es) of a corresponding author(s) indicated were included, therefore the number of papers included in this analysis was smaller than the actual total number of publications per country; a publication was considered to be a multiple countries publication when more than one country was mentioned in affiliations. A collaboration network analysis was conducted in Biblioshiny and interpreted based on the visual properties (overall organization, clusters, and sparse areas) and local metrics that analyze the relation of a single node to the rest of the network (for a detailed description of the local metrics, see [53]).

Finally, two types of keyword analyses were performed for an in-depth understanding of thematic developments in the research field – frequency-based calculation and thematic mapping. Frequency-based analysis was in turn conducted on the individual keywords level and

on the cluster level. For the latter, it was ensured that the same keyword cluster was not mentioned in the same paper record more than once. For that, after merging the keywords in the bigger clusters, the duplicates were removed. As the analysis was performed on multiple levels of clusters (e.g., from electrolyte to the types of metals within metal RFB systems), total numbers of the keywords in clusters might vary from smaller level to the bigger one. For example, in a paper A, on the smallest level there were two different metal materials mentioned; but when we move to the more general level of 'Inorganic', one of those keywords will be removed as a duplicate. We chose this way to be able to look at the field on the paper level. At the same time, the numbers of keywords in clusters do not sum up into a total number of papers as one paper could mention keywords from multiple thematic clusters. Yet, it was possible to compare keyword clusters from different levels, as only a minor overrepresentation of more general clusters (organic and hybrid) was detected, which did not impact a general trend observed in the performed analysis. Keywords from the "Methods" and "No cluster" groups were not included in this analysis, as they did not convey any meaningful results for the study.

The thematic mapping allowed us for the analysis of the conceptual structure of the research field. Based on the co-occurrence of keywords in publications, they form thematic networks, or clusters, which are labeled after the most frequent keyword(s) in the network. Each of the thematic clusters had to appear a minimum of five times per thousand documents to be considered in the analysis. Clusters are then evaluated with Callon's density or development degree and Callon's centrality or relevance degree, where density measures the internal strength of

connections in the network and centrality measures the weight of connections of a network with other networks [54]. Based on these two measurements, each of the clusters is attributed to one of the four quadrants:

- Motor themes (high density and high centrality) are characterized as both well-developed and important for the structure of the research field.
- Basic themes (low density and high centrality) are relevant for the field but have relatively weak internal ties; such themes are transversal and rather important for different areas in the field.
- Highly developed and isolated niche themes (high density and low centrality) have tight internal connections but only marginal importance for the field; these themes are very specialized.
- Lastly, themes that are assigned to emerging or declining (low density and low centrality) are both weakly developed and peripheral. [55]

Only a subset of the database was used for this analysis (performed in Biblioshiny), which included publications on different types of electrolyte materials (i.e., those publications that had at least one keyword from the ‘inorganic’, ‘organic’ and ‘hybrid’ clusters mentioned in the authors’ keywords), resulting in 2.358 records. Keywords that were not attributed to any cluster were excluded from the analysis. Thematic mapping was performed on the keywords in their original ‘unclustered’ configuration on two levels – on the dataset that included only keywords related to electrolyte materials (i.e., keywords not included in the ‘inorganic’, ‘organic’ and ‘hybrid’ clusters were excluded from the analysis) and on the dataset with all the keywords. The first level allows for the investigation of thematic formation around electrolyte materials in relation to other materials (in total 75 most frequent keywords were included); the second level puts the electrolyte material topic in the context of other relevant themes present in the research field (in total 260 most frequent keywords were included). Number of keywords included in the analysis was restricted by the bibliometrix package limitations.

Where a temporal delineation was relevant, 40 years of research were split into three sub-periods. The first cutting year is 2010 as in 2011 the entire RFB field set off, according to the empirical evidence presented further in the Results section. Since most research activity in the field was concentrated in the period after 2011, these 10 years were halved, making 2016 the second cutting year.

The review protocol summarizing the decisions on data extraction, cleaning, and the analysis, as well as the data, scripts, and the result reports are provided in the Supplementary data (Appendix B).

3. Results

3.1. Basic publication trends

The analysis of the annual scientific production in the RFB research field (Fig. 2) demonstrates that, with a relatively low growth rate between 1981 and 2003, annual production steadily increased after 2004 and doubled in 2011, which was followed by rapid growth. Notably, over 90 % of the total publications were written within the last decade. Peaks in global and local citations can be observed in the years 1988, 1992 and 2011 (i.e., papers published in these years had an exceptionally high impact). The publication that contributed most to the peak in 1988 (358 global citations) is the article by Rychcik and Sklyllas-Kazacos [77], which described the construction and performance of an all-vanadium redox flow system. Two globally (531 and 442 global citations, respectively) and locally (56 and 48 local citations, respectively) impactful papers published in 1992 are both by Sun and Sklyllas-Kazacos, which focus on (i) the increased energy efficiency of a vanadium redox cell when using a thermally activated graphite felt electrode [78]), and (ii) the dramatic improvement in the electroactivity of

graphite felt with concentrated sulfuric acid in the vanadium redox cell when surface modification of this material is applied [79]. Together, these three articles formed the foundation in the research of vanadium-based RFB systems.

The peak in mean citations per year in 2011 was primarily caused by two publications which have the highest global impact not only in that year, but also in the entire dataset (Table 1).

In the first paper by Dunn et al. [80], existing battery systems applicable to grid energy storage were reviewed, including RFBs (referred to as low-cost systems) sodium-sulfur, and lithium-ion batteries. The second paper by Yang et al. [81] provided a deeper insight into different electrochemical energy storage technologies, as well as the status and challenges associated with the materials, chemistries, and technologies; RFBs were reviewed along with sodium-beta alumina membrane batteries, lithium-ion batteries, and lead-carbon batteries. As both papers are reviews without a specific focus on RFB systems, they seem to have become major diffusers of knowledge about this technology outside RFB research field. At the same time, as both publications are among the most locally cited papers, with Yang et al. (2011) at the top of the list, they also have a high impact within the field. Another frequently cited review paper published in 2011 is authored by one of the pioneers in the field Maria Sklyllas-Kazacos and her colleagues, who provided an overview of RFB systems and their hybrid alternatives and critically discussed technical aspects, challenges, and limitations, as well as economic and environmental consequences.

Maria Sklyllas-Kazacos, the fourth most productive scholar in the field (Table 2), remained a single prominent publishing author until the first wave of 2004–2010 when more researchers entered the RFB scientific sector (Fig. 3).

During the next wave that started in 2011, more than half of the 30 most productive authors joined the research field. A detailed author analysis provided more details on the profiles of most outstanding scholars of the field. Xianfeng Li and Huamin Zhang are the two most locally impactful authors. Their publications on the topic also received the highest number of citations outside the field and they maintain high ranks in productivity (Table 2). Both scholars are affiliated with the same Chinese organization. The third most productive and second most impactful by m-index scientist of the field, Tianshou Zhao, is also affiliated with China. Overall, 60 % of most impactful authors conduct their research in China.

For all the three researchers, the RFB field appears to be rather marginal or supplemental to their other research interests as the share of the number of publications in the database is relatively low in relation to their global number of publications. In contrast, for Lei Wei (Hong Kong) and Xiaoliang Wei (USA), the RFB technology constitute the biggest proportion of their research activity. Another observation is a clear male prevalence in the field as only two out of 20 most impactful researchers are female – Maria Sklyllas-Kazacos (Australia) and Zhimin Nie (USA).

3.2. Affiliations, countries and networks

According to the affiliation analysis (Fig. 4), the most productive and impactful affiliation in the RFB research field is the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS). Since its entry in 2004, CAS has been demonstrating a rather fluctuating yet overall growing publication activity with a surge in productivity in 2011. However, CAS is a large research cluster that includes a long list of universities, institutes, schools, and other research organizations all over China. This may explain the significant gap between CAS and the second most productive affiliation, the Korea University of Science and Technology (UST). Although UST joined the RFB research field among the latest, only in 2010, the university’s productivity growth pace was rather rapid. However, in the last two years, there has been a substantial decrease in its productivity – by more than half compared to the 2019 peak in total publications.

The University of New South Wales, one of the pioneers in the field, has been a stable contributor since its first publication in 1988. It is also

Fig. 2. Annual production and trends (TP: total production; GC/Y: mean global citation per year; LC/Y: mean local citations per year).

a relatively highly cited affiliation. On the contrary, Argonne National Laboratory and the University of California did not produce any research related to RFB technology after their first publications made around the same time, until after 2011, when the whole research field grew significantly. That year, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory joined the field and quickly became the second most cited affiliation. North China University of Science and Technology entered the field of RFB research the latest, in 2015, and has been demonstrating a fast growth rate since then. Based on the results presented in this and previous subsection, 2011 can be assumed to have become a turning point for research on RFBs, with many scholars and research organizations joining or becoming significantly more active and grow in influence in the field after this year.

Collaboration network analysis allowed for harvesting further insights on interactions between the most prominent research organizations in the field (Fig. 5). With eleven affiliation clusters identified, generally, the network is well-connected, however, some communities appear to have more connections between each other than other – particularly, blue, orange, and green clusters; brown cluster is mostly connected to the blue one; there are more sparse areas around the purple, pink and red clusters. The highest number of thicker edges in the blue cluster indicate that this community is the most cooperative in the network.

CAS, with the highest degree centrality,¹ is the most powerful and influential actor in the whole network. The Joint Center for Energy Storage Research has the second largest number of direct connections in the network with a degree centrality, however, significantly lower relative to CAS (0.517). A betweenness centrality² additionally identifies CAS as the most powerful ‘bridge’ that connects all the communities in the network and influences the information flows within it (196.404). Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (139.613) and Korea University of Science and Technology (122.926) are two other crucial ‘intermediates’ between their communities and other groups in the network. According to the closeness centrality,³ Pacific Northwest National Laboratory is also the main ‘broadcaster’ of the network and is placed so that they could spread the information across the network the quickest (0.012). CAS is the second important ‘spreader’ in the network (0.011).

¹ A number of edges that a node has on a 0–1 scale, relative to the node with the highest number of the edges (i.e., 1) (see Abbasi et al. [53]).

² A number of times a node lies on the shortest path between other nodes (see Abbasi et al. [53]).

³ A sum of reciprocal distances of a node to all other nodes in the network (see Abbasi et al. [53]).

The research dominance of the top publishing organizations affiliated with China and the USA is outstanding. Generally, these two countries are leading in scientific productivity and the total number of citations in the RFB research field, followed by South Korea, although with a significant gap in these two indicators (Fig. 6). A different picture occurs when analyzing the impact of countries in the field based on their scientific impact. This way, France appears to have the biggest global influence in the field with relatively few publications made, followed by Oman and Pakistan with even less publications that, however, received a relatively high number of citations.

A regional overview helped to identify other important research actors in the research field. In the Europe, besides France that leads globally, the Netherlands, Belgium, and the UK are the next most impactful publishers in the region. Germany stands out as another highly productive and very well-cited country internationally but is considerably behind the leading actors in Europe based on the metric of scientific impact. While the USA remains dominant in all indicators in Northern America, the most productive countries in Asia, China, and South Korea, do not lead in scientific impact, ranking eighth and tenth respectively. Pakistan and Oman are the most impactful actors in this region, followed by Israel and Singapore. India is the third biggest contributor to the research field, according to the scientific productivity indicator.

Australia is an important player in the field both regionally and globally. Taking the lead by all parameters in Oceania, Australia is also one of the top ten of most productive and most cited countries, and it ranks sixth by average citation per publication worldwide. South Africa and Mexico are the absolute leaders in Africa, and Latin America and the Caribbean, respectively. Nevertheless, the overall influence of these two regions on the entire scientific field is relatively low.

A different perspective on the global research field emerges from the corresponding authors’ analysis and a share of multiple country publications. Here, China and the USA are leading by the number of multiple countries’ publications; however, the share of papers published by them cooperatively with other countries is among the lowest. Despite a great impact on the entire RFB field, these countries are mainly internally oriented in their research and produce most of their work in relative isolation from the global scientific community. The same pattern can be observed for other primary influencers in the research field according to the collaboration network analysis (see below, Fig. 8), specifically Germany and the UK. The only exception is Spain, with more than one third of its publications written collaboratively with other countries. In contrast, Malaysia and Singapore demonstrate high levels of cooperativeness, with 54 % and 50 % of total articles published as a result of international collaboration. Conversely, South Korea has the lowest share of the multiple countries’ publications.

A temporal resolution of countries’ scientific productivity generally

Table 1
Top 20 publications with highest local impact.

Author(s) (PY)	Title	Source title	LCS	GCS	Type
Yang, Zhang, Kintner-Meyer, Lu, Choi, Lemmon & Liu (2011)	Electrochemical Energy Storage for Green Grid	Chemical Reviews	1016	3434	R
Wang, Luo, Li, Wei, Li & Yang (2013)	Recent Progress in Redox Flow Battery Research and Development	Advanced Functional Materials	755	999	A
Skyllas-Kazacos, Chakrabarti, Hajimolana, Mjalli & Saleem (2011)	Progress In Flow Battery Research and Development	Journal of the Electrochemical Society	741	1096	R
Dunn, Kamath & Tarascon (2011)	Electrical Energy Storage for The Grid: A Battery of Choices	Science	724	9022	R
De Leon, Frías-Ferrer, González-García, Szánto & Walsh (2006)	Redox Flow Cells for Energy Conversion	Journal of Power Sources	647	896	R
Weber, Mench, Meyers, Ross & Gostick (2011)	Redox Flow Batteries: A Review	Journal of Applied Electrochemistry	603	1272	R
Li, Zhang, Mai, Zhang & Vankelecom (2011)	Ion Exchange Membranes for Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRB) Applications	Energy & Environmental Science	502	730	R
Soloveichik (2015)	Flow Batteries: Current Status and Trends	Chemical Reviews	459	659	R
Nguyen & Savinell (2010)	Flow Batteries	Electrochemical Society Interface	429	185	A
Lin, Chen, Gerhardt, Tong, Kim, Eisenach, Valle, Hardee, Gordon, Aziz & Marshak (2015)	Alkaline Quinone Flow Battery	Science	418	578	R
Parasuraman, Lim, Menictas & Skyllas-Kazacos (2013)	Review of Material Research and Development for Vanadium Redox Flow Battery Applications	Electrochimica Acta	417	550	R
Leung, Li, De León, Berlouis, Low & Walsh (2012)	Progress In Redox Flow Batteries, Remaining Challenges and Their Applications in Energy Storage	Rsc Advances	385	656	R
Alotto, Guarnieri & Moro (2014)	Redox Flow Batteries for the Storage of Renewable	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	335	674	R

Table 1 (continued)

Author(s) (PY)	Title	Source title	LCS	GCS	Type
	Energy: A Review.				
Schwenze, Zhang, Kim, Li, Liu & Yang (2011)	Membrane Development for Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries	ChemSusChem	322	397	R
Kim, Park, Kim, Kim, Dou & Skyllas-Kazacos (2015)	A Technology Review of Electrodes and Reaction Mechanisms in Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries	Journal of Materials Chemistry A	317	407	A
Ding, Zhang, Li, Liu & Xing (2013)	Vanadium Flow Battery for Energy Storage: Prospects and Challenges	Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters	298	372	R
Sun, Chen, Zhang, Han & Luo (2010)	Investigations on Transfer of Water and Vanadium Ions Across Nafion Membrane in an Operating Vanadium Redox Flow Battery	Journal of Power Sources	285	328	A
Xi, Wu, Qiu & Chen (2007)	Nafion/Sio2 Hybrid Membrane for Vanadium Redox Flow Battery	Journal of Power Sources	282	382	A
Aaron, Liu, Tang, Grim, Papandrew, Turhan, Zawodzinski & Mench (2012)	Dramatic Performance Gains in Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries Through Modified Cell Architecture	Journal of Power Sources	275	329	A
Jiang, Wu, Yu, Qiu & Xi (2016)	A Comparative Study of Nafion Series Membranes for Vanadium RFBs	Journal of Membrane Science	160	293	A

PY: publication year; LCS: local citation score; GSC: global citation score; A: article; R: review.

confirms the global and regional leadership trends, identified previously (Fig. 7). China and the USA have maintained their research output rates throughout the years, whereas South Korea and Germany took leading positions after 2011. In contrast, one of the leading countries in the first two periods, the UK, gave up its leadership in the last five years. Generally, the number of countries participating in the field is growing, although at a decelerating pace. Between 2017-2021, only 16 countries have entered the field compared to the 26 new active national participants that emerged between 2011-2016.

For a better understanding of the dynamics between the countries involved in the field, a collaboration network analysis was conducted (Fig. 8). There are two major clusters of countries (blue and red) working tightly with each other, as they have the highest concentration of connections between each other in the network. Turkey and Cyprus formed the smallest cluster (dark green). The rest of the nodes did not form any community (18 countries). Around the smallest dark green cluster and individual nodes, there are many sparse areas with mostly one or two edges per node. Although the network appears to be well connected on the general level, it is evident that most of the collaboration occurs within and between the red and blue communities.

Consistently with the results of the analysis for affiliations' cooperation, China has the most influence and power in the network (degree centrality – 1), shortly followed by the USA (0.721). USA also leads in

Table 2

Top 20 most productive authors in the RFB field.

Authors	Affiliation	Country	NP	TGC	TLC	%	h-index	m-index	G
Zhang, Huamin	Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	143	9092	2226	37 %	55	2.90	M
Li, Xianfeng	Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	137	7213	2286	39 %	47	3.62	M
Zhao, Tianshou	Southern University of Science and Technology	China	92	4051	912	20 %	38	3.46	M
Skyllas-Kazacos, Maria	University Of New South Wales	Australia	83	8718	720	39 %	45	1.25	F
Yan, Chuanwei	Institute of Metal Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	74	2255	377	33 %	24	1.20	*
Wang, Wei	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	USA	72	7419	263	77 %	41	3.15	M
Xi, Jingyu	Tsinghua University	China	63	4564	636	46 %	36	1.90	M
Brushett, Fikile Richard	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA	58	2630	246	53 %	28	2.33	M
Liu, Jianguo	Institute of Metal Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	55	1749	301	53 %	20	1.43	*
He, Zhangxing	North China University of Science and Technology	China	54	1459	134	43 %	25	2.08	M
Walsh, Frank C.	University of Southampton	UK	50	5636	522	11 %	37	2.06	M
Cheng, Jie	Zhejiang Tianneng Energy Technology Co., Ltd.	China	47	752	36	42 %	14	0.82	M
Liu, Jun	Changsha University of Science and Technology	China	44	7998	183	8 %	30	2.14	M
Dai, Lei	North China University of Science and Technology	China	41	1227	84	24 %	21	2.33	M
Wei, Xiaoliang	Indiana University-Purdue University Indianapolis	USA	40	4543	162	82 %	31	2.58	M
Sprenkle, Vincent L.	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	USA	39	4002	141	35 %	27	2.25	M
Wei, Lei	Hong Kong University of Science and Technology	Hong Kong	38	2075	437	83 %	26	2.89	M
Wang, Ling	North China University of Science and Technology	China	38	1012	79	18 %	20	2.22	M
Nie, Zhimin	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	USA	38	3816	123	27 %	28	2.15	F
Liu, Le	Tsinghua University	China	38	1851	90	41 %	24	2.00	M

NP: number of publications; TGC: total global citations; TLC: total local citations; %: proportion of the number of publications in the database in relation to the global number of publications; G: gender; M: male; F: female. *Profiles of researchers were not found.

Fig. 3. Research output over time of top 20 most active authors in the RFB research field (ranked by research output).

betweenness centrality which identifies it as the ‘gate keeper’ for the information flows within the network. Another actor of the red cluster, Germany is the second biggest ‘bridge’ (393.366), followed by Spain from the blue cluster (370.982). The UK is identified as a main ‘broadcaster’ in the network (closeness centrality - 0.0103), which allows for the quickest dissemination of information across the network. The USA (0.0097), Germany (0.0096) and China (0.0095) follow it in the ‘spreading’ tempo. Spain has the highest closeness centrality in the blue cluster and the fifth highest in the entire network (0.009).

3.3. Content analysis based on keywords

An analysis of 30 most frequent keywords used by authors gives a first snapshot of the conceptual structure of RFB research field (Table 3). Keywords related to electrolyte and membrane are the most dominant ones, with most of them rapidly growing in their frequency in the last years. Although vanadium and vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) are by far the most popular keywords, zinc-based and organic chemistry alternatives are promptly increasing their influence. Similarly, state of

charge became one of the most frequent topics on technical performance in the last decade. Keywords related to renewable energy technology appear in the field in the context of their coupling with RFBs. Photovoltaics occur more and more often among the keywords in the RFB research field, whereas wind seems to lose the attention of publishing researchers. ‘Fuel cell’ keyword frequency also increased over time, however, in publications covering a variety of aspects: from their performance characteristics to performance of the materials in both setups.

A clearer picture of the thematic distribution in the field emerges from the keyword cluster analysis (Fig. 9). A particular focus on the electrolyte in the research field is prominent, with overall dominance of RFBs based on vanadium and other metals, such as zinc, iron and lead. Nevertheless, in the last five years, interest in metal-based systems is slowly getting replaced by other alternatives, mostly organic materials. Research on inorganic metal-free options and hybrid systems remains relatively stagnant in the field. Another observation is that most of research lays in the technical domain, related to either RFB system components like electrode and membrane, and technical performance of the battery. A rather low share of keywords is related to policy and

Fig. 4. Research output over time of top 30 research organizations (ranked by scientific productivity).

Fig. 5. Collaboration network among most productive affiliations (number of nodes: 50; number of isolated nodes: 3, excluded from the visual).

management and non-technical performance (i.e., sustainability and economic performance) as well as to the studies comparing RFBs with other ES technologies.

As the primary focus of the RFB research field is electrolyte materials, an evolution of the keywords inside the three clusters related to this topic, namely ‘inorganic’, ‘organic’ and ‘hybrid’ clusters, was analyzed (Fig. 10). Although cluster analysis demonstrates clear dominance of vanadium in the field, thematic maps, generated both in isolation to other non-material keyword clusters and in relation to them, reveal a more nuanced picture. Already in the first less research-active period, there were a bunch of niche themes exploring alternative metals, such as lead, uranium, and neptunium, and organic systems. Between 2011-2016, interest in non-vanadium chemistries shrank, pushing research on alternatives, that occur only in combination with vanadium, to the periphery of the field. Organic-based systems have established themselves firmly in the last period. Research on aqueous organic RFBs and quinone appear to be the most developed and

connected to the structure of the research field. Zinc-based systems constitute a few isolated and highly specialized themes in the last period (Fig. 10, A-C).

Interestingly, when analyzed in the wider context of research outside of electrolyte materials over entire period of 40 years, themes on zinc-based systems lose in their relative density, whereas organic and aqueous organic systems persist in their high development and importance for the field, as they remain basic and motor themes, respectively (Fig. 10, D). A hybrid lithium-air flow battery forms a developed research theme, however, of low importance for the field. A renewable energy theme is highly relevant for different areas of the research field. Notably, the second most frequent keyword in this cluster is a main competing storage technology, lithium-ion battery. Finally, as keywords related to sustainability, economic performance, and policy do not appear in the thematic map, we can conclude that these topics are not very prominent in literature focusing on electrolyte materials (Fig. 10, D).

Fig. 6. World map (SP: scientific productivity; SI: scientific impact; TC: total number of citations; MCP: % of multiple countries publications; DRC: Democratic Republic of Congo; UAE: United Arab Emirates).

Fig. 7. Temporal split of countries' research output (NC: number of countries).

A more precise look into the research field revealed that there is more electrolyte material diversity as it appears in absolute numbers. Analysis of the spatially distributed research output on non-vanadium RFB allows for further investigation of where the research comes from (Fig. 11). The absolute majority of 20 most scientifically active (by research output parameter) countries explore all possible alternatives to vanadium, putting more emphasis on other inorganic options, such as metal- and non-metal systems (30 % on average). The UK and the Netherlands have >50 % of their research on other inorganic materials. Less than half of countries dedicate an above average share (>11 %) of their research to

organic materials, the second most popular option, led by the USA (25 %), Malaysia and Spain (both 18 %), and Canada and Portugal (both 17 %). Only 6 % of research on electrolyte materials on average includes hybrid RFBs. France is the only country included in the analysis that prioritizes research on hybrid systems (19 %) over the organic ones.

4. Discussion and conclusions

In this study, we have carried out a bibliometric analysis of academic literature (articles, conference papers and reviews) published in the RFB research field in order to provide a comprehensive overview of associated knowledge base and directions of search. While first publications in the field date back to the 1980s, research activities gained momentum only after the millennium. The increase in the number of publications has been particularly strong since 2011. The fact that this 'turning point' correlated with the publication of two exceptionally highly cited reviews on energy storage technologies indicates that this intensification of research activities went along with an increase in attention paid to energy storage options more generally.

In terms of the directions of search within the field, vanadium-based redox flow batteries have received the strongest attention by far, which reflects the dominance and relative maturity of this flow battery type [15]. Our analysis generally highlights electrolytes as the key focal area within the research field. Considering the huge impact of this system component on the performance and costs of flow batteries [14,56], this does not come as a surprise either. At the same time, research on vanadium-based systems has recently declined, while alternative electrolyte materials, especially organic materials, have gained increased attention. It is plausible that this development is related to the cost, sustainability and availability issues associated with vanadium. However, it is also important to note that the sustainability performance of organic electrolytes depend on the specific material and the components used in other parts of the system [29]. Our keyword analysis also

Fig. 8. Countries' collaboration network (number of isolated nodes: 5, excluded from the visual).

illustrates that most of the research has remained in technical realms. In other words, relatively little research has been conducted on wider innovation aspects such as economic performance, sustainability or policy and management.

In terms of the geographical distribution of the research field, China was clearly the most productive country, followed by the USA, South Korea, and Germany; taken together, the member countries of the European Union showed productivity rates similar to the USA. At the same time, China was behind the USA and the European Union in terms of scientific impact. While collaboration between USA and China was strongest in absolute terms, both countries performed rather poorly with regard to the relative share of multiple country publications. In this context, countries like Pakistan, Singapore or Mexico were leading, which is likely to be explained by their peripheral position in the research field and the comparatively high added value of international collaboration, which is also consistent with the exceptionally high scientific impact of these countries. Our network analysis further identified the USA as the most influential actor within the global collaboration network (i.e., it had the most power over the information flows), whereas the UK was able to disseminate information across the network most effectively.

With regard to the research organizations, the Chinese Academy of Sciences, which is a giant cluster of many research institutions and universities, was dominating the research field and was also the most powerful actor and information 'bridge' in the organizational collaboration network. Korea University of Science and Technology was the second most influential (by number of publications) and also an important actor that influenced the information flows within collaboration network. Pacific Northwest National Laboratory quickly became the second most cited affiliation after joining the field in 2011 and another influential network actor. Generally, half of the 30 most productive research organizations joined the field in or after 2011.

The variation in the geographic distribution of knowledge development raises important questions in terms of the spatial factors that influence the scientific production of a region or a country. In previous

research, scholars have already stressed that the potential existence of a ubiquitous global opportunity set for innovation activities is not reflected in innovation practices [38]. Instead, innovation activities are the outcome of cross-scalar networks, where global networks characterized by a high degree of transferability are intertwined with regional, 'sticky' networks [38,57]. As a result, global innovation systems are still shaped by national and regional systems of innovation [58,59]. While our results confirm these observations, they also lay the foundation for further investigations of the key factors that influence scientific productivity at the regional level. For instance, what are the reasons for the strong scientific productivity of Germany compared to other EU countries or what explains the high scientific impact of Singapore's RFB research?

Another key question that arises from our study relates to the relationship between knowledge creation and technology adoption. Our results indicate potential barriers for technology adoption. First, the identified knowledge network shows that the most productive countries and affiliations are not only the most powerful in the network but are also the ones that show rather low degrees of collaboration. As a result, there is the risk that especially more tacit forms of knowledge (i.e. knowledge that cannot be shared through publications but can only be attained through learning by doing) do not diffuse as widely as would be needed for the acceleration of the innovation system. The second potential barrier relates to the directions of search in terms of the electrolyte, which is a key element of flow batteries. While the innovation systems literature highlights widely shared visions and dominant designs as indicators for a mature technological field [37], our study indicates that the search activities for electrolyte materials are increasing, rather than decreasing.

The above-described search activities not only include novel chemistries but also additives to (i) increase solubility, (ii) widen the electrochemical window of water, and to (iii) increase the kinetics of the redox active species. At the same time, the scale of up the single cell testing of these materials into multi cell setups or even stacks is mostly described for vanadium battery technology [22,23,26]. This represents a

Table 3
Top 30 mostly frequently used keywords.

Cluster	Top 30 most frequent keywords	Total frequency	Rank		
			1981–2010	2011–2016	2017–2021
Electrolyte	vanadium ^a	1422	2	1	1
	electrolyte	80	na	7	14
	non-aqueous redox flow battery ↑	49	na	63	18
	aqueous redox flow battery ↑	41	na	77	24
	zinc-bromine redox flow battery ↑	36	na	93	30
	zinc-nickel flow battery ↑	35	102	118	33
	organic redox flow battery ↑	34	na	399	28
Membrane	membrane ↑	113	277	6	5
	anion exchange membrane ↑	82	28	11	9
	ion-exchange membrane ↑	78	4	20	11
	nafion	71	15	9	22
	sulfonated poly(ether ether ketone)	54	375	23	23
	proton exchange membrane	42	79	27	40
	composite membrane	36	18	36	51
Electrode	electrode	79	20	10	12
	graphite felt	73	36	13	15
	carbon felt	58	17	18	21
	porous electrode ↑	42	42	151	26
Tech. performance	state of charge ↑	63	88	28	16
	energy efficiency ↑	59	13	29	19
	electrochemical performance	47	200	15	34
	capacity decay	37	na	35	41
	load frequency control ↑	37	270	31	46
Application	renewable energy ↑	89	8	14	8
	fuel cell ↑	69	34	19	13
	microgrid	47	na	16	32
	photovoltaics ↑	43	40	107	25
Other storage	wind	43	5	17	100
	lithium-ion battery	50	na	21	27
	supercapacitor	36	24	33	61
	Number of keywords	5653	435	1835	4376
Total fq of keywords	16,885	804	4602	11,479	

The sign “↑” indicates that a keyword rank increased in the last period.

General keywords that were not attributed to any cluster or described methods were included in the analysis, but excluded from the Table as they did not convey meaningful results.

^a Due to space constraints, ‘vanadium redox flow battery’ keyword was merged with ‘vanadium’, which are top two most frequent overall with the total frequencies of 1273 and 149, respectively.

Fig. 9. Content analysis based on keyword clusters (Sust: sustainability; P&M: policy and management. Note that electrolyte in this context refers to a solution of the redox active species).

Fig. 10. Thematic maps of electrolyte material research (A-C: performed only on the dataset with only keywords related to electrolyte materials, $N = 75$; D: performed on the same dataset with all keywords, excluding keywords without a cluster, $N = 260$).

Fig. 11. Research on alternative materials per country (number of papers only on electrolyte materials is specified in parenthesis next to each country).

further barrier to technology development: due to unavailability of equipment and/or materials, promising results are often not transferred from university labs to the next scale. Furthermore, the lack of data for scale up batteries makes the economic and ecologic assessment more challenging as they depend on the actual performance of the battery [60].

It is important, however, to note that the relationship between scientific knowledge creation and technology adoption is not straightforward. In fact, the innovation systems approach was developed out of criticisms of naïve conceptualizations of the innovation process, which depict research, development and adoption as consecutive phases.

Following such a linear understanding would assume that once ‘enough’ research has been conducted, the development and adoption stages would follow inevitably. In contrast to this is the all-too-familiar notion of the “valley of death”, which refers to the frequently made observation that many technological fields suffer from the inability to implement and commercialize scientific discoveries. In the case of the RFB technology, a relative lack of research on non-technical performance, policy and management could be evidence of a yet slow adoption of the technology, regardless of unprecedented publication rates on technological aspects of RFBs. Against this background, the innovation system approach describes the innovation process as one characterized by the

iterative interplay among a range of different activities including not only the development and diffusion of knowledge and entrepreneurial activities but also the mobilization of resources and creation of markets or legitimacy [35,36]. Hence, it would be an interesting direction for future research to complement our study with an in-depth analysis of other relevant innovation activities in the global RFB innovation system.

Despite the well-grounded results that could be derived from this study, the research method has several limitations mostly related to the data and its nature. Firstly, the database included only publications in English. Although one can argue that for the global perspective on the research field, publications in English would be sufficient, there is a chance that some data on co-authorship of papers published in other languages in regions like Asia, Europe or Latin America and the Caribbean was not included in the analysis. The inconsistency in the data provided by Scopus should be also taken into consideration, particularly concerning different authors with twin surnames and initials and multiple Scopus pages for the same authors. Moreover, keywords can only tell an imperfect story about general trends and topics in the field and their absence in some of the papers in the corpus put even further limitations to the keyword analysis.

Lastly, while our in-depth content analysis helped us locate where the knowledge base of the research field grew or is growing stronger, some conclusions drawn from this might deviate from the actual thematic developments in the field. Due to the sole reliance on quantitative productivity metrics, quality aspects of the research contributions by certain publications, scholars, affiliations, and countries could have been overlooked. Furthermore, the retrospective bias inherent to bibliometric analysis [61] poses the risk of underrepresenting very recent cutting-edge research such as work on standardized assessment metrics [62], organic flow batteries [63,64] or cost-effective membranes [65]. Studying more recent developments in a systematic way, for instance through qualitative literature reviews, is thus an important endeavor for future research. In addition, patent and market analysis should be conducted to confirm identified trends and reveal further insights.

The main objective of this bibliometric study was to sketch a comprehensive overview of the RFB research field, with its main regional and global actors, trending themes and emerging directions of search. Based on that, it was possible to spotlight topics that did not receive enough attention yet. The sustainability performance of the batteries is one of the research lines that was not substantially covered, which is critical for a technology whose development is driven by environmental considerations and sustainable energy transition. Incomparability of life cycle assessment studies, across both different ESS and RFB technologies, and gaps in systematic understanding of environmental impacts of non-vanadium RFB systems negatively contribute to the technology adaptation [60,66].

Research and innovation targeting cost reduction are also highly relevant for the RFB market competitiveness [11,67–71]. Cost reductions can be achieved by economies of scale principles as we have seen it in the past decade for Li-ion batteries. Synergies with other related technologies such as fuel cells may give the required incentive in the future to also reduce the manufacturing costs, particularly of the power components. In order to leave the niche segment, the cost of basically all components of the battery, including membrane, electrolyte, electrode materials, frames etc. and the periphery (hydraulic and electric components) needs to be lowered [72]. This requires multidisciplinary research from both applied and fundamental point of view (e. g., replacement of vanadium in the electrolyte, more efficient electrodes for vanadium, widening of electrochemical window of water [73]. Scale up is still underrepresented in research but is central to technology adoption and more efforts are needed to support these activities by relevant funding bodies. The same applies to the policy aspects, which do not stand out in the content analysis, even though they are highly relevant for the technology uptake. Finally, growing interest in organic and other alternative RFB systems calls for further deeper investigations of these research directions and their prospects [11,70,74,75].

In summary, our comprehensive bibliometric analysis has revealed the dynamic landscape of research trends within the redox flow battery domain, showcasing the immense progress since the 2000s and the intensified interest reflecting broader energy storage considerations. Our study has unveiled not only a focus on electrolytes, pivotal for battery performance and cost but also a notable transition from vanadium-based systems toward organic materials, driven by the imperatives of cost, sustainability, and material availability. Still, the most mature technology is based on vanadium chemistry, which is the main type of RFB technology deployed so far. Furthermore, by shedding light on the relatively nascent attention given to the economic, sustainability, and policy dimensions of the RFB innovation system, our analysis calls for a multi-faceted expansion of research beyond the technical sphere.

Our insights into the geographic and organizational disposition of the RFB research underscore the complex interplay between scientific productivity and regional innovation capabilities, providing an impetus for further exploration of the underlying factors that propel or hinder research productivity and impact across different locations. The disparities in global knowledge networks suggest that fostering more collaborative and multilateral research could become pivotal for bridging the gaps between knowledge creation and technological diffusion within the RFB sector. Particularly, the observed trends in electrolyte innovation signifies not a mere increase in research activities but, potentially, a paradigm shift in the search for alternative chemistries that could redefine RFB technologies and their market viability-if the demands on performance and cost are met.

Our bibliometric investigation serves as a critical basis for the RFB research community, enabling stakeholders to identify underexplored domains, potential collaborations, and strategic pathways to innovation. New funding schemes and concepts are needed to enable to bridge the valley of death, i.e. to scale the technology from lab based excellent research to working demonstrators and, finally, products. The emergent themes, from cost reduction to sustainability assessment, underscore the necessity for a concerted, interdisciplinary approach that integrates insights from science, engineering, economics, and policy to navigate the complexities of modern energy storage technologies.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Victoria Yavorskaya: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michael Kriechbaum:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Stefan Spirk:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data has been provided as Supporting materials

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Appendix A. Overview of keyword clusters

General cluster	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
System components	Electrolyte (2617)	Inorganic (2074)	Metal (1954)	Single-metal (1854)	vanadium (1500); zinc (117); iron (108); lead (68); cerium, manganese, copper, bismuth, chrome, cobalt (<50 each); uranium, nickel, aluminium, ruthenium, neptunium, iridium, tin-bromine (≤10 each)
				Dual-metal (98)	zinc-x (62); iron-x (21); nickel-x, cobalt-iron, cerium-vanadium, copper-x, vanadium-bismuth, aluminium-x (<10 each)
	Membrane (971)	Organic (288) Hybrid (119) Fluorinated (156) Non-fluorinated (378)	Metal-free (159)	Quinoids (149); Tempo (35); other (20)	
				metal/organic-air (73); organic-inorganic (28)	
				nafion (86); pvdf (28); vanadion, ptfe (<20 each); pfsa (2)	
Electrode (1035)	Carbons (540) Metals and metal oxides (135)	composites (121); speek (59); imidazoles, other non-fluorinated membranes (48 each); sulfones, sio2 and hydroxides, polyimide, nanocomposites, peek and ether ketones (<40 each); polyacrylonitrile, cellulose, polyester, polypropylene and polyethylene (≤10 each); graphene oxides, biopolymer, evoh, sulfonated fullerenes (<5 each)			
		carbon (362); graphite (144); graphene (84)			
Housing (334)	titanium (32); zinc (31); tin, tungsten, nickel, platinum and iridium (<15 each); gold, zirconium, copper, lead, molybdenum, aluminium, chromium, cobalt, tantalum, cerium, iron, silver (≤5 each)				
Performance	Flow channel (159); Stack (126); Frame (5)				
	Technical performance (1254)			Sustainability performance (121)	
	Comparison with other storage technologies (238) Economic performance (141)			Policy and management (62)	
Implementation	Methods (1101)				
	Application (666)				
	System operation (315)				
Not clustered (2195)					

Keyword frequency is specified in parenthesis. Duplicate keywords in each record were removed after every level of aggregation.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.113093>.

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